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Overhead line and Insulated Cables

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Investigation of Defect Insulation Systems with Deferent Artificial Cavities Consisting of High Voltage Power Cable

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SUMMARY - The insulation lifetime of power cables is determined by several factors. One of the most important of these is the occurrence of partial discharge (PD) at the dielectric. The ability to detect and locate a PD source is limited by attenuation of the high frequency PD pulses as they propagate through the cable to the sensor. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the high frequency response of such cables. The aim of this thesis is to develop an accurate frequency-dependent cable model for detecting and locating degraded insulation regions on power cables, caused by partial discharge activities. Numerical methods can calculate field distribution in the vicinity of nonstandard shape cavities, which generate PDs, and are difficult to calculate by analytical methods. The simulated results show the important influence of the shape of cavity on the electric stress within it. Cavity stress enhancement increases as the permittivity of the dielectric increases. The increase is greater for cavities with large diameter to thickness ratios. A cavity with its axis parallel to the applied field direction has a higher stress enhancement. In addition, the stress distribution in the cavities is smaller for spherical cavities than for cylindrical types. An investigation into the possibility of detecting different PD patterns and signals when conducting PD tests using different sensor bandwidths is also presented in this thesis. The occurrence of discharge activity was created by an artificial defect manufactured in the single core cable insulation. The artificial defect generated an internal discharge and was used to investigate the PD signal propagation on cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE) cable. Capacitance coupled external sensors have been applied for the PD detection measurements and the results show that these external sensors have a number of advantages compared to high frequency current transformer (HF-CT) sensors for the detection of PD pulses.

Keywords – Investigation of insulation ageing due to treeing - Conventional applied voltage, time, frequency and temperature - Partial Discharge Measurement Laboratory.

1.Introduction

The use of XLPE insulation for high-voltage power cable is increasing worldwide. Consequently, the number of new installed high-voltage XLPE power cable is also increase in the power network. The new cable systems are installed in the field and inaccurate assembling of cable accessories could result in the presence of defects. The after-laying test is performed in the new cable system to check the quality of cable system installation. One of the most important applications in the after-laying test is partial discharge measurement due to the characteristics of the XLPE insulation which is very sensitive to PD activity. Therefore, the after-laying test is important to certify a good start of the lifetime of the cable system. The main problem in off-line PD detection as part of after-laying test is the complexity between PD detection methods, testing voltages and PD occurrence. For that reason, the investigation of the typical installation defects, their related effect and characteristic based on different PD detection methods and different voltage energizing are very important. In this thesis, three artificial defects that represent different type of PD situation, surface discharge and electrode-bounded cavity, are created in the joint of full-scale test set-up of 150 kV transmission power cable systems. Investigation is done by making simulation of electric field distribution profile in order to see the field enhancement due to the presence of defects and then applying a PD measurement by using different energizing and PD detection method to investigate the PD properties and detectability of each defect. In addition, several measurement issues that influence the HF/VHF/UHF un-conventional PD measurement are also investigated in this thesis to provide a better understanding and performance of un-conventional PD detection in after-laying test of HV cable system

2. Partial Discharge definition and terminology

According to IEC-60270 Standard, Partial Discharge (PD) is defined as localized electrical discharge that only partially bridges in the insulation between conductors, and which can or cannot occur adjacent to a conductor [1]. Usually, each partial discharge appears as a fast-electrical pulse with a duration of a few to hundreds of nanoseconds. In the IEC-60270 standard, the partial discharge pulse (PD pulse) is defined as a current or voltage pulse that results from a partial discharge occurring within the object under test. The pulse is measured using suitable detector circuits, which have been introduced into the test circuit for the purpose of the test [2]. The PD pulse usually has a relatively small magnitude and energy and appears because of the enhancement of electrical field due to local concentrations or low dielectric strength media. However, the low energy associated with the PD pulses

can deteriorate the dielectric material over time, which can then lead to a complete breakdown of the insulation. In addition, the presence of PD produces localized heat and generates a complex chemical reaction that may accelerate the material ageing. Ultraviolet radiation from the PD may also cause unavoidable defects in the insulation. Electrical trees filamentary carbonized tracks in solids or on surfaces may also be developed because of high localized stress within a defect site. Therefore, continuous presence of the PDs will significantly increase the deterioration rate of the insulation materials, and thus reduce their expected lifetime. The PDs occur when the applied electric field stress exceeds a critical value. This situation causes some local discharge to occur. The corresponding voltage is the PD inception voltage. The PD inception voltage is defined as: the applied voltage at which the repetitive PDs are first observed in the test object, when the voltage applied to the object is gradually increased from a lower value at which no PDs are observed. The associated field stress that occurs in the test object at

inception voltage is designated as the PD inception stress [3]. In a similar way, the PD extinction voltage is defined as: the applied voltage at which repetitive PDs cease to occur in the test object, when the voltage applied to the object is gradually decreased from a higher value at which PD pulse quantities are observed [20]. In practice, the PD inception and extinction voltages are greatly affected by the nature of the test object. Environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and pollution may affect the PD inception and extinction voltages, particularly surface discharges on outdoor insulators. Accordingly, the field stress that occurs in the test object at extinction voltage is designated as the extinction stress [4]. Figure 1 illustrates the equivalent circuit diagram of the conventional electrical discharge detection circuit. Conventional detection method is the most common detection method to detect partial discharges since it is convenient, sensitive and easier to calibrate

Figure 1: Conventional Electrical Discharge Detection Equivalent Circuit.

From the circuit at Figure 1 (a), there are three capacitive elements, namely Cx, Cy and Cz. Cx represents the capacitance of the body insulation, which is equal to the total

capacitance of the test object. Cz represents the small cavity present that generates PDs while Cy is the insulation in series with the cavity. By applying mesh analysis on the circuit, the voltages across the three elements can be determined by the following equations:

$$V_x = V_y + V_z$$

When the voltage across Vz is sufficient to cause a breakdown inside the cavity, Vz will be short-circuited by breakdown, thus the voltage eventually will almost reach to zero, and subsequently Vx and Vy are connected in parallel since both are not affected. In order to correct this situation, small amounts of charge flow from Cx towards Cy to neutralize the voltages, thereby causing small voltage to dip across the test object. Voltage dips cannot be detected directly in practical sense, thus by connecting an external coupling capacitor of equal value to the test object, greater sensitivity is obtained (Figure 1 (b)). Small impedance Z is connected in parallel with Cx, and for discharges occurring in Cz, some charge has to flow from Cx to Cy (current flow shown in blue). At the same time, some discharges will flow in the opposite direction from CB to Cy (current flow shown in green). This flow of charge constitutes a small current to flow from impedance Z back to CB, and it can be detected since it flows through Z. For better accuracy in results, a large signal must be developed across Z for a given discharge in the cavity. This can be done simply by increasing the value of CB as much as is possible, so that most discharges can be neutralized by Cy.

3. Artificial Defects for the Investigation

For the investigation purpose there are three artificial defects which can be applied in the cable joint. These defects are the missing of outer semi-conductive screen, extra semi-conductive

screen in the joint and the electrode-bounded cavity. These three artificial defects represent the different case of PD occurrences. The first and second artificial defect represents the surface discharge along the interface of insulation material. This type of PD can result in failure of cable system even if the extruded insulation is totally immune to PD-induced electrical tree initiation [5]. The third artificial defect represents the case of electrode-bounded cavity between the outer semi-conductive screen and the cable insulation. Investigation is done by modeling the defect by a soft field plotting program to get an electric field behavior in the cable system due to the presence of defect and then applying two different AC voltages to energize the test setup which consist of these three defects in order to generate PD activities and then two PD detection methods are used for the measurement [6].

Jarot Setyawan [7] reported at the improper on-site installation of the cable accessories can produce defects in the cable system that can result in the cable system failure in short-long operation time span and show that three artificial defects that represent different types of installation defects are applied to the test set-up and investigation is done by modeling the defect with a soft field plotting program to get the electric field behavior and then applying two different PD measurement methods to get the PD properties for each defect.

The investigators [8] have dealt with the influence of spherical voids parameters upon the induced charge. They show that a quantitative interpretation of induced charge requires knowledge not only of the void location, geometry and dimensions, void gas pressure and composition, but also of the void orientation with reference to the applied field.

Peter H.F. Morshuis [9] has studied the degradation of solid dielectric due to internal partial discharge and concluded that the interaction between the PD process and the aging dielectric is strong. In the course of the aging process the PD mechanism changes. This is well observed in the changing PD pulse shape and in the changing PD phase pattern. He also showed that the PD resistance of a dielectric in many cases can be improved significantly by mechanical pre-stressing.

4. Discharges on cables

Partial discharges are very harmful in solid insulated cables. In most cases, discharges that are detected during normal operation will lead to a breakdown. The time from partial discharge ignition to the final breakdown depends on the discharge type and place in the cable. A partial discharge phenomenon is random and there is always some statistical variation between the times to the breakdown. Depending on the discharge's type and place the time to the breakdown varies from a few hours to a few years [10]. In extruded medium voltage cables there are many places where partial discharges may ignite. Partial discharges might appear in voids or cavities within the insulation or at interfaces between insulation and semi-conductive screens, in broken neutral or in electrical trees initiated from protrusions, contaminants, voids or water trees [11]. Figure 3.1 presents typical defects in solid insulation.

Figure 2: Typical defects in solid insulation.

Cavities, protrusions, contaminants, screen interruptions and de-laminations are all defects that may form during cable manufacture. De-lamination may also form due to external pressure which strangles the cable. Water trees are formed due to the ingress of moisture in cable insulation. Cracks might form when insulation is subjected to extreme temperature conditions. The metallic shield might break due to excessive fault currents or corrosion. Rough handling during installation may damage the outer protective layers, insulation or insulation screen and thus speed up the aging process. Today an acceptance test for medium voltage cables is conducted after manufacturing. To pass this test the partial discharge magnitude in the cable should be less than 5 pC at $1.5 U$ [12]. There is some variation in this threshold value and measurement voltage between different standards. As an example, the IEC 60502_2 threshold is 10 pC at $2.0/1.7 U$ [13] When cable manufacturing and testing is properly conducted new cables should not contain any harmful defects.

Partial discharges may also take place in the cable's metallic shield if it is harmed. The type of discharges in those cases is spark discharges that take place between metallic connections. It has been shown that the discharge magnitude in these kinds of defects is in a range of hundreds of pC [14]. This type of partial discharges seldom results in cable failure [15]. However, it is important that the continuity of the cable shield is preserved for safety reasons. Today it is common to install cables with fully watertight structure, which in theory should decrease water treeing. Faults related to manufacturing mistakes have been reduced due to improved manufacturing techniques and quality control. Cable plowing has become more and more common also at medium voltage level. It is important to control how this affects the amount of damages caused to the cables during installation [16].

5. Partial discharge in a cavity

A cavity is a gas-filled void within a dielectric material which may be created during manufacture, installation or during operation of a high voltage system. To ensure PD activity occurs in a cavity, the electric field in the cavity must exceed the breakdown strength of the gas, which is called the inception field, E_{inc} and there must also be a free electron available to initiate an electron avalanche. Cavities are formed during fabrication, installation and operation of the cable system. Once the size of the cavity reaches the critical limit required to initiate a discharge, a self-sustained discharge is unlikely to develop due to lack of initiatory electrons instead

PD initially occurs as a single discharge event triggered each time a free electron is initiated in the cavity due to background radiation. The rate of these discharges depends on the cavity size as well as on the excitation voltage. figure (3-1) show the test setup and Figures (3-2), (3-3) presents the PD inception voltage as a function of cavity size (spherical cavity, flat cavity, ellipse cavity and plate cavity) with depth 2 mm for XLPE cable sample 18/30kV - 1x 400 mm² approximately length 13 m. PD can also be initiated in lower size cavities during transient overvoltage conditions. This PD may be maintained by the residue voltage resulted during the PD activity during the transient condition. Residue voltage depends on the cavity size, PD repetition and the conductivity of the cavity walls. The critical size for a streamer-like discharge to occur at the cable operating voltage for this case at about a thousand pC, and increase the PD magnitude at $1.73 U_0$ according IEC 60502-2 [17] at 10.7 nC with plate cavity.

Figure 3.1: test setup for XLPE cable sample 18/30 kV-1x400 mm²

Figure 3.2: PD measurements for cable sample 18/30 kV - 1x400 mm², with different forms of the artificial cavity at constant depth 2 mm.

Figure 3.3: PD measurements for cable sample 18/30 kV - 1x400 mm², with different forms of the artificial cavity at constant depth 2 mm.

6. CONCLUSION

I-The experiments showed that growth of cavities between the insulation results in a decrease of the dielectric strength and that breakdown occurs along the cavities. The effect of increasing the interfacial pressure in a cable is probably to limit the extension of cavities between the insulation and therefore prevent the large reduction of the dielectric strength along the interfaces.

II-The laboratory experiments showed with comparing of different forms of the artificial cavity at constant depth 2 mm.

- A. Spherical Cavity
- B. Flate Cavity (Oblate).
- C. Ellipse Cavity
- D. Plate Cavity

The PD level of flate form (Oblate) the artificial cavity increase with increasing KV level with short time

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